

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Benzoic Acids by Lead Tetra-acetate in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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Kinetics of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids by lead tetraacetate (LTA) have been studied in aquo-acetic acid medium under varying conditions. The rates of oxidations show zero order kinetics in both [LTA] and [H⁺], and generally fractional order each in [substrate] and [Ru^{III}]. The rates decrease with the increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent, while increase with the increase in ionic strength of the medium. Two-pathway mechanisms have been considered to explain the observed results and the related rate laws are deduced. The rate constants of the rate-limiting steps and the corresponding activation parameters have also been computed. The rate constants recalculated from the rate laws as the [substrate] and [Ru^{III}] varied, compare reasonably well with the experimental values.

THE chemistry of carboxylic acids is of interest due to their wide synthetic and biological applications.

They are the most important organic compounds that show appreciable acidity¹. Although most of the other classes of organic compounds have been extensively investigated on the mechanistic aspects of their oxidations, there is very little information on the mechanistic aspects of carboxylic acid oxidations². Hence we thought it worthwhile to investigate the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids in aquo-acetic acid under varying conditions.

Experimental

The solution of lead tetraacetate (G.R., E. Merck) in purified acetic acid was standardised before use. Benzoic acids (Sisco) were purified by recrystallisation from methanol and their stock solutions (0.50 mol dm⁻³) were also prepared in purified acetic acid. The ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.20 mol dm⁻³ using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium acetate. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurements: Kinetic measurements were made in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] ≫ [oxidant]. The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.5 × 10⁻³ – 4 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing known amounts of the substrate (0.005 – 0.10 mol dm⁻³), acid (0.005 – 0.10 mol dm⁻³), RuCl₃ (2.0 × 10⁻⁵ – 5.0 × 10⁻⁴), water and acetic acid (to maintain 1 : 1, v/v water-acetic acid), thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the

reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-zero order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and values were reproducible within ±4% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of lead tetraacetate-benzoic acid reactions was determined by equilibrating varying ratios of substrate and oxidant in water-acetic acid medium. Determination of unreacted lead tetraacetate in the reaction mixture showed 1 : 1 molar stoichiometry,

Phenyl acetate was identified by tlc.

Results and Discussion

Results of the study are shown in Tables 1–3 and Fig. 1.

At fixed [HClO₄] and [RuCl₃] with several fold excess of [substrate], the zero order plots, [LTA] vs time were linear for at least two half-lives and the pseudo-zero order rate constants computed from the plots were unaffected by the changes in [LTA]₀. At constant [LTA] and [HClO₄], the rates increased with increase in [substrate] with fractional order kinetics in [substrate]. The plots of *k*_{obs} vs [S] were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates. The variation in [H⁺] at fixed [substrate] and [LTA] had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations (Table 1), establishing zero order kinetics in [H⁺]. The rates increased with increase in [RuCl₃] with varying kinetics in its concentration (Table 2). The plots of *k*_{obs} vs [Ru^{III}] were also linear (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[R-C_6H_4COOH]$; $10^3 [LTA]_0 = 10^4 [Ru^{III}] = 50 [HClO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 303 K, and (ii) k_{obs} vs $[Ru^{III}]$; $10^3 [LTA]_0 = 50 [HClO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [R-C_6H_4COOH]$ (mol dm^{-3}) = 5.0 (a, b, c, e, f), 3.0 (d, g), temp. = 303 K: (a) unsubstituted, (b) *o*-NO₂, (c) *o*-Cl, (d) *o*-Me, (e) *m*-NO₂, (f) *m*-Cl, (g) *m*-Me.

The [substrate] were varied at different temperatures and the constants of the rate-limiting steps were calculated. The activation parameters corresponding to these constants have also been computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots.

The rates increased with increase in ionic strength of the medium in all the cases, while they decreased with increase in acetic acid composition of the medium (Table 3). Addition of lead acetate, the reduced product of the oxidant had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations.

The kinetics of zero order in [LTA] and [H⁺] and generally fractional order each in [substrate] and [Ru^{III}] may be explained by a two-pathway mechanism, a major portion of reaction going through the rate-determining interaction between the substrate and the catalyst. Ru^{III} may interact with the oxidant in a fast step to form Ru^V which in turn abstracts hydrogen from the substrate in the rate-determining step. The detailed mechanism of oxidation is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR Ru^{III}-CATALYSED OXIDATION OF BENZOIC ACIDS (BA) BY LEAD TETRAOXYACETATE (LTA) IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) AT 303 K

$10^3 [LTA]_0$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 [BA]_0^*$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 [Ru^{III}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^2 [HClO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^7 k_{obs}$ (mol $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$)						
				H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Me**	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Me**
0.50	5.0(3.0)	1.0	2.0	4.3	0.80	2.6	6.4	0.62	1.3	3.3
1.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	2.0	4.5	0.79	3.3	6.6	0.63	1.4	3.6
2.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	2.0	4.4	0.79	3.2	6.5	0.65	1.4	3.5
4.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	2.0	4.5	0.76	3.1	6.9	—	1.3	3.5
1.0	0.50	1.0	2.0	—	—	—	1.8	—	0.24	—
1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	1.4	0.40	1.0	3.0	0.37	0.41	1.2
1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.3	0.52	1.6	4.7	0.47	0.62	—
1.0	10.0	1.0	2.0	7.1	1.3	5.8	—	0.8	—	12.2
1.0	5.0(3.0)	0.20	2.0	0.93	—	—	1.8	—	—	1.0
1.0	5.0(3.0)	0.50	2.0	2.3	0.42	1.6	3.8	—	0.91	2.0
1.0	5.0(3.0)	2.0	2.0	7.9	1.7	7.5	12.8	0.94	2.4	5.6
1.0	5.0(3.0)	3.0	2.0	—	2.4	11.3	3.0	—	3.0	—
1.0	5.0(3.0)	5.0	2.0	—	—	—	—	1.8	—	—
1.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	0.50	4.7	0.81	3.3	7.2	0.63	1.4	3.5
1.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	1.0	4.5	0.79	3.3	6.7	0.58	1.4	3.5
1.0	5.0(3.0)	1.0	5.0	4.5	0.77	3.2	6.4	0.62	1.3	3.6

*Values in parantheses are with *o*-Me and *m*-Me BA. **At 293 K.

TABLE 2—KINETIC DATA AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE Ru^{III}-CATALYSED OXIDATION OF BENZOIC ACIDS BY LEAD TETRAACETATE IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM

Orders (<i>n</i>) observed in	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃
[LTA]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
[BA]	0.70	0.42	0.75	0.74	0.33	0.72	1.0
[HClO ₄]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
[Ru ^{III}]	0.93	0.97	1.0	0.84	0.65	0.69	0.80
Activation parameters calculated from <i>k</i> ₁							
<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	68.6	49.1	52.8	43.8	58.4	53.6	
log <i>A</i>	10.6	5.2	7.8	7.1	7.8	7.6	
Δ <i>H</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	62.8	38.9	53.0	41.6	55.0	52.0	
Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-60.7	-155.2	-94.6	-116.6	-107.6	-104.4	
Δ <i>G</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	81.2	85.9	81.7	75.8	87.6	83.7	

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE REACTION MEDIUM ON RATES OF Ru^{III}-CATALYSED OXIDATION OF BENZOIC ACIDS BY LEAD TETRAACETATE IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v)

μ mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁷ <i>k</i> _{obs} (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)			
	H*	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ *	<i>m</i> -Cl*	<i>m</i> -Me**
0	3.3	—	—	—
0.20	4.5	0.78	1.4	3.6
0.40	5.6	0.89	1.6	4.2
0.60	6.5	0.97	1.7	4.5
%HOAc				
30	8.1	1.3	2.4	7.6
50	4.5	0.78	1.4	3.6
70	2.3	0.47	0.71	1.8
80	1.8	0.33	0.52	1.3

*10³ [LTA]₀=20 [BA]₀=10⁴ [Ru^{III}]=50 [HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³ at 303 K. **10³ [LTA]₀=33.33 [BA]₀=10⁴ [Ru^{III}]=50 [HClO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³ at 293 K.

The other minor portion of the reaction may go through all independent path including the uncatalysed path of oxidation. Our efforts to study the uncatalysed reactions were unsuccessful as the reactions were very slow. The combined rate law is

$$k_{obs} = k_1[S][Ru^{III}] + k_0 \text{ (Independent path)} \quad (2)$$

The rate law (2) is in conformity with the observed linearities of the plots, *k*_{obs} vs [substrate] and *k*_{obs} vs [Ru^{III}], with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Fig. 1). The constants *k*₁ and *k*₀ were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of either of the plots. The constants calculated from the plot of *k*_{obs} vs [substrate] were used to predict the constants as the [Ru^{III}] was varied, in all the cases and vice versa.

The recalculated values compared with experimental constants are shown in Table 4. Reasonable agreement between the two sets of values tests the validity of the rate law and provides support to the suggested mechanism. Further, the values of *k*₁ were calculated at different temperatures by varying [substrate] at each temperature. The activation parameters have also been computed from the plots of log *k*₁ vs 1/*T* and log *k*₁/*T* vs 1/*T* (Table 2). Applicability of Hammett equation has also been tested. The equation was found to be valid with substituted benzoic acids for which σ values were available³,

$$\log k_{obs} = -6.3 - 1.33\sigma$$

The negative value for the reaction constant and the kinetic data indicate that electron-releasing

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED CONSTANTS AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES WITH THE VARIATION OF [BENZOIC ACID] AND [Ru^{III}] FOR Ru^{III}-CATALYSED OXIDATION OF BENZOIC ACIDS BY LEAD TETRAACETATE IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v)

10 ³ [Benzoic acid] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁷ <i>k</i> (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)													
	H		<i>o</i> -NO ₂		<i>o</i> -Cl		<i>o</i> -Me		<i>m</i> -NO ₂		<i>m</i> -Cl		<i>m</i> -Me	
	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.	Recal.	Expt.
0.50	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.6	1.8	—	—	0.47	0.24	—	—
1.0	1.1	1.4	0.21	0.40	0.75	1.0	2.6	3.0	0.38	0.37	0.58	0.41	1.4	1.2
2.0	1.9	2.3	0.37	0.52	1.5	1.6	4.6	4.7	0.44	0.47	0.78	0.62	—	—
3.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	6.6	6.6	—	—	—	—	3.1	3.6
5.0	4.2	4.4	0.85	0.80	3.7	3.3	10.7	10.4	0.62	0.63	1.4	1.4	4.7	6.7
10.0	8.1	7.1	1.6	1.3	7.5	5.8	—	—	0.91	0.80	—	—	8.9	12.2
10 ⁴ [Ru ^{III}] (mol dm ⁻³)														
0.20	1.4	0.93	—	—	—	—	2.3	1.8	—	—	—	—	0.76	1.0
0.50	2.4	2.3	0.55	0.42	1.3	1.5	4.0	3.8	—	—	0.77	0.91	1.9	2.0
1.0	4.0	4.4	0.80	0.78	3.0	3.2	6.9	6.6	0.60	0.61	1.4	1.4	3.8	3.6
2.0	7.2	7.9	1.3	1.7	5.6	7.5	12.6	12.8	0.84	0.94	2.6	2.4	7.5	5.6
3.0	—	—	1.8	2.4	8.3	11.3	—	—	1.1	1.3	3.8	3.4	—	—
5.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.6	1.8	—	—	—	—

substituents on the benzene ring of the benzoic acid accelerate the rate of oxidation whereas electron-withdrawing groups retard it.

The constancy of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values indicate the operation of similar mechanisms. The formation of more ordered activated complexes is evident from the relatively large negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values. Further, the plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ was linear with an isokinetic temperature of 262 K, which is lower than the temperature range employed in the present investigation (288–313 K). This may probably indicate that the changes in rate are caused by changes in both $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$.

The observed decrease of rates with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium is in conformity with the Amis concept⁴.

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